

A Simulation Study of Sampling from a Continuous Density Function Using Inverse-CDF and Acceptance-Rejection Methods

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Abstract

In statistics, we frequently encounter complex probability distributions, and generating random samples from them can often be challenging. To address this issue, simulation-based techniques such as inverse-CDF (cumulative distribution function) sampling and acceptance-rejection sampling are commonly employed. This article investigates methods for generating random samples from a particular continuous probability density function (PDF) consisting of two distinct regions and shapes: a triangular distribution on the left of the origin and an exponential distribution on the right. We have considered four different sampling procedures: Inverse-CDF sampling (C1), acceptance-rejection sampling (C2), a hybrid method using inverse-CDF for the exponential region and acceptance-rejection for the triangular region (C3), and another hybrid method where inverse-CDF sampling is applied to the triangular region and acceptance-rejection sampling is implemented for the exponential region (C4). The performance of these methods was assessed by comparing the theoretical and empirical density plots, generated for varying sample sizes (n) and mixture parameter p . Theoretical moments (mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis) of the target distributions were computed and compared with the simulated results. Overall, both singular and hybrid sampling/RNG (random number generation) techniques delivered acceptably well, particularly with large sample sizes. Occasional suboptimal performance was observed for parameters involving higher-order moments when the mixture was asymmetric and the sample size was small, but this does not alter our generally positive assessment of these strategies. Both represent recommendable tools for sampling univariate densities. If forced to choose between these two approaches, our preference would be for the inverse-CDF technique whenever possible, as it provides a direct sampling method. However, acceptance-rejection sampling is more general, being applicable to a broader spectrum of densities.

Keywords: *Inverse-CDF Sampling, Acceptance-Rejection Sampling, Mixture Distribution*

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1. Introduction

Generating random samples from probability distributions is a fundamental aspect of statistical modeling and simulation. This paper focuses on sampling from a selected continuous probability density function, $f(x)$, defined by a triangular shape on the left side of the origin and an exponential shape on the right (Von Hippel, 2005) to illustrate the operational and procedural characteristics of two major random number generation (RNG) approaches. The primary goals of this paper are to: (1) sample from this distribution using two widely employed techniques, and (2) compare the actual versus simulated density plots of $f(x)$ across different sample sizes and parameters to evaluate how properly the random number generation procedures work in terms of minimizing the discrepancies between expectation and reality.

2. Methods

2.1. Overview of Sampling Techniques

The generation of random samples from a given probability distribution is typically an integral part and a core stage of many statistical procedures (see Gao & Demirtas, 2024, and references therein. The complete list appears in the References Section.). Two broadly utilized sampling techniques in this context are inverse-CDF sampling and acceptance-rejection sampling. These methods have practical value and statistical validity, especially when the distribution of interest is complicated.

2.1.1. Inverse-CDF Sampling

The inverse-CDF sampling method (also known as inverse transform sampling) hinges on the foundational property of cumulative distribution functions (CDFs). If a continuous random variable X has a cumulative distribution function $F(x)$, then a random sample from this distribution can be obtained by:

- (1) Generating a uniform random variable $U \sim U(0,1)$,
- (2) Computing the corresponding sample as $X = F^{-1}(U)$, where F^{-1} denotes the inverse of the cumulative distribution function.

2.1.2. Acceptance-Rejection Sampling

Acceptance-rejection sampling is a more general technique that can be applied when direct sampling is impractical or when inverse-CDF sampling is difficult. This method generates samples from a proposal distribution (such as normal and uniform) that is straightforward to sample and chooses to accept or reject the samples based on calculated acceptance probabilities. To simulate a sample for the random variable X with a target distribution $f(x)$, we follow the following steps:

- (1) Generate a candidate sample $X \sim g(x)$, where $g(x)$ is the proposal distribution that is easy to sample from and satisfies the condition: $Mg(x) \geq f(x), \forall x$. Here, M is a scaling constant;
- (2) Compute the acceptance probability: $A(x) = \frac{f(x)}{Mg(x)}$;
- (3) Accept or reject X :
 - Generate $U \sim U(0,1)$,
 - Accept X if $U \leq A(x)$,
 - Otherwise, reject X and repeat the process.

2.2. Density of Interest

The probability density function chosen to illustrate two RNG algorithms is given by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} (1-p) \left(1 + \frac{1-p}{2p} x\right), & \text{if } -\frac{2p}{1-p} \leq x \leq 0, \\ (1-p)e^{-x}, & \text{if } x > 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $0 < p < 1$ (Von Hippel, 2005). The distribution is a mixture of triangular and exponential densities, with the relative weight determined by the mixing proportion p . Specifically, small values of p place greater emphasis on the exponential component, whereas large values of p assign more weight to the triangular component. For different values of p , the densities as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Densities for different values of mixing proportion, p .

2.3. Inverse-CDF Sampling Procedure

In this section, we describe how to generate random samples from the target continuous density function using the inverse-CDF sampling method for a triangular-exponential mixture distribution, taking the density function given in Section 2.2 as a basis. The procedure is carried out through the CDF, $F(x)$, and its inverse $F^{-1}(u)$, which are derived as follows:

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} (1-p)x + p + \frac{(1-p)^2 x^2}{4p}, & \text{if } -\frac{2p}{1-p} \leq x \leq 0, \\ 1 - (1-p)e^{-x}, & \text{if } x > 0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The inverse CDF, $F^{-1}(u)$, is given by:

$$F^{-1}(u) = \begin{cases} -\frac{2p}{1-p} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{u}{p}} \right), & \text{if } u \leq p, \\ -\ln \left(\frac{1-u}{1-p} \right), & \text{if } u > p. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The steps for generating random samples from the target distribution using the inverse-CDF method are as follows:

- (1) Generate a uniform random variable u from the interval $[0,1]$.
- (2) Determine whether $u \leq p$ or $u > p$, where p is a pre-defined parameter of the mixture distribution, with $0 < p < 1$.
- (3) If $u \leq p$, compute $x = -\frac{2p}{1-p} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{u}{p}} \right)$.
- (4) If $u > p$, compute $x = -\ln \left(\frac{1-u}{1-p} \right)$.
- (5) The resulting value of x is a random sample from the target distribution.

2.4. Acceptance-Rejection Sampling Procedure

To generate samples from the target density function using acceptance-rejection sampling, we implemented the following steps for the two distinct regions of the function.

- For $x \leq 0$ (Triangular Region):
 - (1) Proposal Distribution: Propose a sample x from a uniform distribution $x \sim U\left(-\frac{2p}{1-p}, 0\right)$.
 - (2) Acceptance Probability: Compute the acceptance probability $A(x) = \frac{f(x)}{M_1 g_1(x)} = \frac{(1-p)\left(1 + \frac{1-p}{2p}x\right)}{2p \cdot \frac{1-p}{2p}} = 1 + \frac{1-p}{2p}x$.
 - (3) Acceptance Step: Accept x if a uniform random variable $u \sim U(0,1)$ satisfies: $u \leq A(x)$.
- For $x > 0$ (Exponential Region):
 - (1) Proposal Distribution: Propose a sample x from a uniform distribution $x \sim U(0,10)$.
 - (2) Acceptance Probability $A(x) = \frac{f(x)}{M_2 g_2(x)} = \frac{(1-p)e^{-x}}{10(1-p) \cdot \frac{1}{10}} = e^{-x}$.
 - (3) Acceptance Step: Accept x if a uniform random variable $u \sim U(0,1)$ satisfies $u \leq A(x)$.

2.5. Comparison of Four Sampling Strategies

To sample from the target density function, which consists of two distinct parts (a triangular part and an exponential part), we considered four different sampling procedures:

- Procedure C1: This method applies inverse-CDF sampling to the entire density function.
 - Procedure C2: This method utilizes acceptance-rejection sampling for the entire density function.
 - Procedure C3: This is a hybrid approach. Inverse-CDF sampling is used for the exponential part of the density function, while acceptance-rejection sampling is applied to the triangular part.
 - Procedure C4: This is another hybrid approach, where inverse CDF sampling is applied to the triangular part, and acceptance-rejection sampling is used for the exponential part.
- The performance of these procedures will be assessed by generating samples from the target density function across various combinations of sample sizes n and mixing parameter p .

2.6. Properties of the Density under Consideration

Here, we derive the first four raw moments of the random variable following the afore-mentioned mixture density. These moments yield the parameters of interest for the simulation study described below. The raw moments are:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[X] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} xf(x)dx = \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x(1-p)\left(1 + \frac{1-p}{2p}x\right)dx + \int_0^{\infty} x(1-p)e^{-x}dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[\int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 xdx + \frac{1-p}{2p} \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^2dx \right] + (1-p) \int_0^{\infty} xe^{-x}dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[-\frac{2p^2}{(1-p)^2} + \frac{1-p}{2p} \cdot \frac{8p^3}{3(1-p)^3} + 1 \right] \\
&= 1-p - \frac{2p^2}{3(1-p)},
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[X^2] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2f(x)dx = \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^2(1-p)\left(1 + \frac{1-p}{2p}x\right)dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^2(1-p)e^{-x}dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[\int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^2dx + \frac{1-p}{2p} \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^3dx \right] + (1-p) \int_0^{\infty} x^2e^{-x}dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[\frac{8p^3}{3(1-p)^3} - \frac{1-p}{2p} \cdot \frac{4p^4}{(1-p)^4} + 2 \right] \\
&= 2(1-p) + \frac{2p^3}{3(1-p)^2},
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[X^3] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^3f(x)dx = \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^3(1-p)\left(1 + \frac{1-p}{2p}x\right)dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^3(1-p)e^{-x}dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[\int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^3dx + \frac{1-p}{2p} \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^4dx \right] + (1-p) \int_0^{\infty} x^3e^{-x}dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[-\frac{4p^4}{(1-p)^4} + \frac{1-p}{2p} \cdot \frac{32p^5}{5(1-p)^5} + 6 \right] \\
&= 6(1-p) - \frac{4p^4}{5(1-p)^3},
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[X^4] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^4 f(x) dx = \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^4 (1-p) \left(1 + \frac{1-p}{2p} x\right) dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^4 (1-p) e^{-x} dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[\int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^4 dx + \frac{1-p}{2p} \int_{-\frac{2p}{1-p}}^0 x^5 dx \right] + (1-p) \int_0^{\infty} x^4 e^{-x} dx \\
&= (1-p) \left[\frac{32p^5}{5(1-p)^5} - \frac{1-p}{2p} \cdot \frac{32p^6}{3(1-p)^6} + 24 \right] \\
&= 24(1-p) + \frac{16p^5}{15(1-p)^4}.
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

We can find the mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis via the above results:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Mean} &= \mathbb{E}[X] = 1 - p - \frac{2p^2}{3(1-p)}, \\
\text{Variance} &= \mathbb{E}[X^2] - (\mathbb{E}[X])^2 = 1 + \frac{p^2}{3} + \frac{2p^3(3-2p)}{9(1-p)^2}, \\
\text{Skewness} &= \frac{\mathbb{E}[(X - \mathbb{E}[X])^3]}{\text{Var}(X)^{3/2}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[X^3] - 3\mathbb{E}[X]\mathbb{E}[X^2] + 2(\mathbb{E}[X])^3}{\text{Var}(X)^{3/2}}, \\
\text{Kurtosis} &= \frac{\mathbb{E}[(X - \mathbb{E}[X])^4]}{\text{Var}(X)^2} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[X^4] - 4\mathbb{E}[X^3]\mathbb{E}[X] + 6\mathbb{E}[X^2](\mathbb{E}[X])^2 - 3(\mathbb{E}[X])^4}{\text{Var}(X)^2}.
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

3. A Simulation Study

The simulation design is as follows: Data were generated through the triangular-exponential density with three levels of sample sizes, small ($n = 100$), moderate ($n = 2,000$), and large ($n = 10,000$) with permutations of two sampling techniques (inverse-CDF and acceptance-rejection) implemented for the triangular and exponential parts that we explained in Section 2.5 (C1 to C4), with five different values of p (0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9). The parameters of interest are the first four moments (mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis) which are often regarded as the benchmark set of quantities that typically characterizes a distribution. The experiment is repeated $N = 1,000$ times; the number of simulation replicates was 1,000. Estimates for four parameters were obtained at each replication; they were combined into a few quantities that we describe below for evaluation. Our assessment is predicated upon the following major accuracy and precision criteria:

Raw bias (RAWBIAS) is the difference between the true value of θ and average estimate across N replications. $\text{RAWBIAS} = E[\hat{\theta}] - \theta$. Obviously, smaller absolute magnitude is better.

Standardized bias (STBIAS) is the relative magnitude of the raw bias to the overall uncertainty in the system. It is defined as $\text{STBIAS} = 100 \times \frac{\theta - E[\hat{\theta}]}{\text{SE}(\hat{\theta})}$, where SE stands for standard error. If it exceeds 50% in either direction, then the bias begins to have a noticeable adverse impact on efficiency, coverage, and error rates (Demirtas & Doganay, 2012).

Percentage bias (PCTBIAS) is the relative magnitude of the raw bias to the true parameter value. $\text{PCTBIAS} = 100 \times \frac{\theta - E[\hat{\theta}]}{\theta}$. The acceptable range for PCTBIAS is usually taken as less than 5% in either direction. (Demirtas et al, 2017)

Root-mean-square error (RMSE) is an integrated measure of bias and variance. It is arguably the best criterion for evaluating $\hat{\theta}$ in terms of combined accuracy and precision. RMSE is defined as $\sqrt{E_{\theta}[\hat{\theta} - \theta]^2}$.

In addition to the above-mentioned evaluation measures to assess how far our AEs (average estimates) from the true parameter values, we included SE (standard error of the estimates) and empirical confidence intervals using the 5th and 95th percentiles (CI_L and CI_U , respectively) of the estimates across all 1,000 simulation replicates in Tables 1-9. Note that it is possible to construct theoretical bounds and calculate the coverage rate, we chose to report the 90%

empirical confidence interval, reflecting a belief that it is more appropriate in this context. Under the preceding specification, RAWBIAS, STBIAS, and PCTBIAS are pure accuracy measures, while RMSE, CI_L , and CI_U are the hybrid measures of accuracy and precision.

Results for three different sample sizes are presented in Tables 1-9. Due to space limitations, we only report results for $p = 0.1, 0.5,$ and 0.9 (full results can be obtained through the supplementary file). The number of significant digits varies by reported quantity. Column 2 lists the true values of the four parameters of interest, while Column 3 specifies the RNG method. Subsequent columns display average estimates (AE) and a few evaluation metrics. Recall that the simulation evaluates four data generation methods (C1 to C4) for the target probability density function, combining the triangular and exponential components. The methods include inverse-CDF sampling, acceptance-rejection sampling, and hybrids of the two, applied to three different sample sizes ($n = 100, 2000, 10000$) and mixing proportion p ($0.1, 0.5,$ and 0.9).

For the mean and variance parameters, all four methods yielded a very satisfactory performance, as measured by all accuracy and precision-related quantities. All deviations are within acceptable limits, and there is a decent match between the true values and the averaged empirical values across simulation replicates in all scenarios examined in this work. Clearly, empirical confidence intervals got narrower as n became larger. The comparative weights of the two parts of the density, dictated by p did not seem to make a substantial difference. Furthermore, no discernible differences were detected across different sampling strategies.

For parameters regarding the higher order moments (skewness and kurtosis), the overall pattern is the same, however, the performances are occasionally choppy and divergent. Skewness is a measure of asymmetry, and kurtosis is a measure of elongation or peakedness/flatness. Given the construction of a mixture density, the mixing proportion p has implications in terms of symmetry and peakedness behavior. In our example, when the density is dominated by the exponential part (small p) and the sample size is not large, the proximity between theoretical and actual data trends weakens.

Histograms of sampled data are compared against the theoretical probability density function (PDF) to assess the accuracy of each method under varying conditions. Inverse-CDF and acceptance-rejection sampling results are represented by blue and red lines in Figures 2-4, respectively. These visualizations use a single replication of data generation to illustrate typical single-replication behavior relative to the theoretical density. While averaged trajectories across replications could have been used, they would mask replication-specific variability and provide unrealistic precision for practical applications. All sampling methods (C1-C4) yield reasonable approximations of the target density, particularly with large sample sizes. However, the inverse-CDF approach shows a slight advantage over acceptance-rejection for small sample sizes at extreme mixing proportions (e.g., $p = 0.1$ or 0.9).

Table 1. Simulation results when drawing 100 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.1$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI_L	CI_U
$p = 0.1$	Mean	C1	0.8885	-0.0041	-3.99%	-0.46%	0.1018	0.1019	0.7255	1.0613
		C2	0.8917	-0.0009	-0.88%	-0.10%	0.0965	0.0964	0.7376	1.0526
		C3	0.8917	-0.0009	-0.96%	-0.10%	0.0951	0.0950	0.7364	1.0610
		C4	0.8918	-0.0008	-0.82%	-0.09%	0.0972	0.0972	0.7368	1.0588
	Variance	C1	0.9901	-0.0140	-4.96%	-1.40%	0.2829	0.2831	0.5886	1.4696
		C2	0.9934	-0.0107	-3.82%	-1.06%	0.2793	0.2794	0.6045	1.4998
		C3	0.9925	-0.0116	-4.08%	-1.15%	0.2844	0.2845	0.6030	1.4941
		C4	0.9909	-0.0132	-4.72%	-1.31%	0.2785	0.2786	0.6081	1.5318
	Skewness	C1	1.7834	-0.2043	-36.83%	-10.28%	0.5548	0.5909	1.0679	2.8486
		C2	1.7813	-0.2065	-40.13%	-10.39%	0.5146	0.5542	1.1074	2.7766
		C3	1.7655	-0.2222	-42.64%	-11.18%	0.5213	0.5664	1.1013	2.7659
		C4	1.7800	-0.2077	-37.37%	-10.45%	0.5557	0.5930	1.0715	2.8425
	Kurtosis	C1	7.1824	-1.7687	-46.71%	-19.76%	3.7869	4.1778	3.5031	14.6281
		C2	7.1732	-1.7778	-51.31%	-19.86%	3.4646	3.8926	3.5960	14.3723
		C3	7.0425	-1.9086	-55.12%	-21.32%	3.4627	3.9523	3.5888	13.9740
		C4	7.2209	-1.7302	-45.21%	-19.33%	3.8268	4.1980	3.5284	14.6590

Table 2. Simulation results when drawing 100 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.5$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.5	Mean = 0.1667	C1	0.1704	0.0037	3.25%	2.22%	0.1139	0.1139	-0.0057	0.3667
		C2	0.1651	-0.0016	-2.13%	-0.96%	0.0754	0.0754	0.0433	0.2935
		C3	0.1677	0.0010	1.27%	0.61%	0.0802	0.0802	0.0413	0.3078
		C4	0.1660	-0.0007	-0.92%	-0.42%	0.0765	0.0765	0.0394	0.2941
	Variance = 1.3056	C1	1.3208	0.0153	4.95%	1.17%	0.3084	0.3087	0.8885	1.8890
		C2	1.3064	0.0008	0.27%	0.06%	0.2924	0.2923	0.8898	1.8160
		C3	1.3081	0.0026	0.86%	0.20%	0.3008	0.3007	0.8947	1.8599
		C4	1.3001	-0.0054	-1.87%	-0.42%	0.2902	0.2902	0.8952	1.7846
	Skewness = 1.3022	C1	1.1621	-0.1401	-28.94%	-10.76%	0.4840	0.5036	0.5017	2.0492
		C2	1.1654	-0.1369	-26.74%	-10.51%	0.5119	0.5296	0.4707	2.0910
		C3	1.1509	-0.1513	-31.75%	-11.62%	0.4765	0.4997	0.5240	2.0503
		C4	1.1331	-0.1692	-35.36%	-12.99%	0.4784	0.5072	0.5161	2.0400
	Kurtosis = 6.4653	C1	5.4161	-1.0491	-42.77%	-16.23%	2.4528	2.6666	2.9788	10.3226
		C2	5.4950	-0.9703	-33.80%	-15.01%	2.8703	3.0285	2.8689	10.5592
		C3	5.3972	-1.0681	-40.88%	-16.52%	2.6127	2.8214	3.0142	10.4011
		C4	5.2978	-1.1675	-45.82%	-18.06%	2.5478	2.8014	2.9660	10.4181

Table 3. Simulation results when drawing 100 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.9$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.9	Mean = -5.3000	C1	-5.3020	-0.0020	-0.44%	0.04%	0.4593	0.4591	-6.0392	-4.5282
		C2	-5.2960	0.0040	0.99%	-0.07%	0.3983	0.3981	-5.9242	-4.6254
		C3	-5.3099	-0.0099	-2.39%	0.19%	0.4132	0.4131	-6.0226	-4.6539
		C4	-5.3055	-0.0055	-1.35%	0.10%	0.4067	0.4065	-6.0027	-4.6736
	Variance = 20.7100	C1	20.4844	-0.2256	-9.20%	-1.09%	2.4527	2.4618	16.4783	24.6571
		C2	20.5381	-0.1719	-7.26%	-0.83%	2.3664	2.3715	16.6836	24.5528
		C3	20.6042	-0.1058	-4.50%	-0.51%	2.3489	2.3501	16.8395	24.6938
		C4	20.5939	-0.1161	-4.95%	-0.56%	2.3467	2.3484	16.7532	24.3299
	Skewness = -0.4893	C1	-0.4867	0.0026	1.55%	-0.54%	0.1696	0.1695	-0.7731	-0.2166
		C2	-0.4785	0.0108	6.45%	-2.20%	0.1668	0.1671	-0.7531	-0.1988
		C3	-0.4767	0.0126	7.74%	-2.58%	0.1629	0.1633	-0.7381	-0.2115
		C4	-0.4851	0.0042	2.61%	-0.86%	0.1620	0.1620	-0.7454	-0.2219
	Kurtosis = 2.4337	C1	2.4512	0.0174	5.36%	0.72%	0.3257	0.3260	2.0282	2.9983
		C2	2.4407	0.0069	2.33%	0.29%	0.2976	0.2976	2.0353	3.0123
		C3	2.4321	-0.0016	-0.56%	-0.07%	0.2841	0.2840	2.0206	2.9292
		C4	2.4456	0.0118	3.98%	0.49%	0.2979	0.2980	2.0191	2.9783

Table 4. Simulation results when drawing 2000 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.1$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.1	Mean = 0.8926	C1	0.8931	0.0005	2.19%	0.06%	0.0227	0.0227	0.8560	0.9315
		C2	0.8921	-0.0005	-2.35%	-0.06%	0.0217	0.0217	0.8567	0.9266
		C3	0.8921	-0.0005	-2.46%	-0.06%	0.0209	0.0209	0.8592	0.9264
		C4	0.8909	-0.0017	-7.67%	-0.19%	0.0219	0.0219	0.8541	0.9276
	Variance = 1.0041	C1	1.0062	0.0021	3.26%	0.21%	0.0649	0.0649	0.9005	1.1171
		C2	0.9997	-0.0044	-6.99%	-0.44%	0.0635	0.0636	0.8999	1.1101
		C3	1.0020	-0.0021	-3.52%	-0.21%	0.0608	0.0609	0.9065	1.1086
		C4	0.9957	-0.0084	-13.66%	-0.83%	0.0612	0.0617	0.8999	1.1000
	Skewness = 1.9877	C1	1.9724	-0.0153	-8.71%	-0.77%	0.1758	0.1763	1.7200	2.2928
		C2	1.9501	-0.0376	-25.28%	-1.89%	0.1487	0.1533	1.7197	2.1987
		C3	1.9794	-0.0083	-4.33%	-0.42%	0.1925	0.1926	1.7214	2.2837
		C4	1.9450	-0.0427	-28.34%	-2.15%	0.1508	0.1566	1.7009	2.2073
	Kurtosis = 8.9511	C1	8.7818	-0.1693	-9.44%	-1.89%	1.7934	1.8005	6.6973	11.8138
		C2	8.5065	-0.4445	-36.65%	-4.97%	1.2129	1.2913	6.7260	10.6607
		C3	8.8984	-0.0527	-2.39%	-0.59%	2.2078	2.2073	6.7455	12.1029
		C4	8.4642	-0.4868	-39.11%	-5.44%	1.2446	1.3359	6.5779	10.7198

Table 5. Simulation results when drawing 2000 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.5$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.5	Mean = 0.1667	C1	0.1681	0.0014	5.51%	0.85%	0.0259	0.0259	0.1259	0.2089
		C2	0.1657	-0.0010	-5.56%	-0.58%	0.0173	0.0173	0.1356	0.1922
		C3	0.1667	0.0001	0.35%	0.04%	0.0174	0.0174	0.1399	0.1961
		C4	0.1667	0.0000	0.24%	0.02%	0.0171	0.0171	0.1389	0.1939
	Variance = 1.3056	C1	1.3078	0.0023	3.41%	0.17%	0.0666	0.0666	1.1993	1.4231
		C2	1.3005	-0.0051	-7.74%	-0.39%	0.0658	0.0659	1.1947	1.4096
		C3	1.3055	-0.0001	-0.10%	-0.01%	0.0663	0.0663	1.2029	1.4225
		C4	1.3018	-0.0037	-5.72%	-0.29%	0.0651	0.0652	1.1974	1.4131
	Skewness = 1.3022	C1	1.2964	-0.0059	-3.96%	-0.45%	0.1483	0.1483	1.0794	1.5527
		C2	1.2803	-0.0219	-16.44%	-1.68%	0.1334	0.1351	1.0784	1.5142
		C3	1.2918	-0.0105	-6.76%	-0.80%	0.1549	0.1552	1.0755	1.5541
		C4	1.2743	-0.0279	-20.97%	-2.14%	0.1331	0.1359	1.0645	1.5117
	Kurtosis = 6.4653	C1	6.4111	-0.0542	-4.47%	-0.84%	1.2135	1.2141	4.9955	8.5632
		C2	6.2622	-0.2031	-22.76%	-3.14%	0.8925	0.9149	5.0078	7.8589
		C3	6.3752	-0.0901	-6.64%	-1.39%	1.3555	1.3578	4.9703	8.5080
		C4	6.2115	-0.2538	-28.32%	-3.93%	0.8963	0.9311	4.9262	7.9323

Table 6. Simulation results when drawing 2000 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.9$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.9	Mean = -5.3000	C1	-5.2953	0.0047	4.75%	-0.09%	0.0995	0.0996	-5.4521	-5.1278
		C2	-5.3042	-0.0042	-4.63%	0.08%	0.0903	0.0903	-5.4513	-5.1587
		C3	-5.3014	-0.0014	-1.65%	0.03%	0.0876	0.0876	-5.4381	-5.1476
		C4	-5.2980	0.0020	2.16%	-0.04%	0.0918	0.0917	-5.4456	-5.1462
	Variance = 20.7100	C1	20.7039	-0.0061	-1.08%	-0.03%	0.5662	0.5659	19.8230	21.6389
		C2	20.7117	0.0017	0.32%	0.01%	0.5320	0.5318	19.8170	21.5901
		C3	20.6924	-0.0176	-3.39%	-0.08%	0.5183	0.5183	19.8508	21.5187
		C4	20.6803	-0.0297	-5.56%	-0.14%	0.5348	0.5353	19.7816	21.5597
	Skewness = -0.4893	C1	-0.4884	0.0009	2.39%	-0.18%	0.0375	0.0375	-0.5505	-0.4285
		C2	-0.4873	0.0020	5.55%	-0.41%	0.0359	0.0359	-0.5461	-0.4315
		C3	-0.4884	0.0009	2.59%	-0.19%	0.0358	0.0358	-0.5486	-0.4291
		C4	-0.4885	0.0008	2.17%	-0.16%	0.0364	0.0364	-0.5514	-0.4298
	Kurtosis = 2.4337	C1	2.4341	0.0004	0.61%	0.02%	0.0670	0.0669	2.3256	2.5455
		C2	2.4316	-0.0021	-3.27%	-0.09%	0.0638	0.0638	2.3282	2.5434
		C3	2.4330	-0.0007	-1.02%	-0.03%	0.0652	0.0652	2.3306	2.5424
		C4	2.4311	-0.0027	-4.17%	-0.11%	0.0636	0.0636	2.3299	2.5384

Table 7. Simulation results when drawing 10000 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.1$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.1	Mean = 0.8926	C1	0.8923	-0.0003	-2.79%	-0.03%	0.0103	0.0103	0.8752	0.9090
		C2	0.8917	-0.0009	-9.53%	-0.10%	0.0093	0.0093	0.8770	0.9069
		C3	0.8931	0.0005	5.27%	0.06%	0.0095	0.0095	0.8771	0.9087
		C4	0.8924	-0.0002	-2.34%	-0.03%	0.0097	0.0097	0.8769	0.9078
	Variance = 1.0041	C1	1.0032	-0.0009	-2.99%	-0.09%	0.0289	0.0289	0.9566	1.0497
		C2	0.9985	-0.0056	-20.63%	-0.55%	0.0270	0.0275	0.9559	1.0449
		C3	1.0055	0.0014	4.84%	0.14%	0.0283	0.0283	0.9607	1.0527
		C4	1.0006	-0.0035	-12.48%	-0.35%	0.0282	0.0284	0.9535	1.0454
	Skewness = 1.9877	C1	1.9858	-0.0020	-2.33%	-0.10%	0.0851	0.0850	1.8587	2.1410
		C2	1.9544	-0.0334	-49.27%	-1.68%	0.0677	0.0755	1.8478	2.0687
		C3	1.9855	-0.0023	-2.76%	-0.11%	0.0819	0.0819	1.8609	2.1340
		C4	1.9569	-0.0309	-44.85%	-1.55%	0.0688	0.0754	1.8498	2.0695
	Kurtosis = 8.9511	C1	8.9375	-0.0136	-1.52%	-0.15%	0.8960	0.8956	7.7412	10.6182
		C2	8.5380	-0.4130	-72.28%	-4.61%	0.5715	0.7049	7.6469	9.5502
		C3	8.9292	-0.0218	-2.56%	-0.24%	0.8530	0.8528	7.8120	10.6450
		C4	8.5581	-0.3930	-68.23%	-4.39%	0.5760	0.6970	7.7163	9.5319

Table 8. Simulation results when drawing 10000 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.5$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.5	Mean = 0.1667	C1	0.1668	0.0002	1.61%	0.11%	0.0112	0.0112	0.1478	0.1846
		C2	0.1665	-0.0002	-2.02%	-0.09%	0.0078	0.0078	0.1539	0.1797
		C3	0.1662	-0.0004	-5.45%	-0.25%	0.0078	0.0078	0.1530	0.1784
		C4	0.1661	-0.0006	-7.37%	-0.35%	0.0080	0.0080	0.1534	0.1797
	Variance = 1.3056	C1	1.3055	-0.0001	-0.28%	-0.01%	0.0305	0.0305	1.2577	1.3549
		C2	1.3033	-0.0023	-7.67%	-0.18%	0.0300	0.0300	1.2543	1.3532
		C3	1.3053	-0.0003	-1.00%	-0.02%	0.0295	0.0295	1.2570	1.3568
		C4	1.3028	-0.0028	-9.13%	-0.21%	0.0302	0.0303	1.2537	1.3547
	Skewness = 1.3022	C1	1.3041	0.0018	2.63%	0.14%	0.0692	0.0692	1.1959	1.4223
		C2	1.2861	-0.0161	-26.06%	-1.24%	0.0618	0.0638	1.1880	1.3822
		C3	1.2998	-0.0025	-3.55%	-0.19%	0.0691	0.0691	1.1977	1.4142
		C4	1.2856	-0.0166	-26.84%	-1.28%	0.0619	0.0640	1.1853	1.3887
	Kurtosis = 6.4653	C1	6.4874	0.0221	3.79%	0.34%	0.5834	0.5835	5.7019	7.4578
		C2	6.2881	-0.1772	-42.10%	-2.74%	0.4209	0.4564	5.6280	7.0156
		C3	6.4548	-0.0105	-1.86%	-0.16%	0.5654	0.5652	5.6884	7.4389
		C4	6.2912	-0.1741	-41.36%	-2.69%	0.4209	0.4553	5.6227	6.9757

Table 9. Simulation results when drawing 10000 samples using four sampling methods ($p = 0.9$).

Scenario	Moments	Method	AE	RAWBIAS	STBIAS	PCTBIAS	SE	RMSE	CI _L	CI _U
p = 0.9	Mean = -5.3000	C1	-5.2983	0.0017	3.76%	-0.03%	0.0451	0.0451	-5.3716	-5.2282
		C2	-5.3011	-0.0011	-2.73%	0.02%	0.0406	0.0406	-5.3682	-5.2354
		C3	-5.3014	-0.0014	-3.60%	0.03%	0.0394	0.0395	-5.3680	-5.2339
		C4	-5.3018	-0.0018	-4.57%	0.03%	0.0400	0.0400	-5.3693	-5.2356
	Variance = 20.7100	C1	20.7122	0.0022	0.90%	0.01%	0.2458	0.2457	20.3194	21.1091
		C2	20.7097	-0.0003	-0.13%	0.00%	0.2434	0.2433	20.3069	21.1068
		C3	20.7178	0.0078	3.23%	0.04%	0.2415	0.2415	20.3178	21.1083
		C4	20.7112	0.0012	0.51%	0.01%	0.2397	0.2395	20.3300	21.1127
	Skewness = -0.4893	C1	-0.4896	-0.0003	-1.64%	0.06%	0.0173	0.0173	-0.5182	-0.4612
		C2	-0.4894	-0.0001	-0.51%	0.02%	0.0159	0.0159	-0.5152	-0.4631
		C3	-0.4894	-0.0001	-0.50%	0.02%	0.0161	0.0161	-0.5145	-0.4631
		C4	-0.4887	0.0006	3.65%	-0.12%	0.0164	0.0164	-0.5169	-0.4621
	Kurtosis = 2.4337	C1	2.4347	0.0010	3.44%	0.04%	0.0292	0.0292	2.3864	2.4813
		C2	2.4335	-0.0002	-0.85%	-0.01%	0.0282	0.0282	2.3868	2.4796
		C3	2.4326	-0.0012	-4.14%	-0.05%	0.0279	0.0279	2.3881	2.4785
		C4	2.4320	-0.0017	-5.73%	-0.07%	0.0294	0.0294	2.3826	2.4798

(a) Simulation plot: $n = 100$, $p = 0.1$.

(b) Simulation plot: $n = 100$, $p = 0.5$.

(c) Simulation plot: $n = 100$, $p = 0.9$.

Figure 2. Histogram and density comparison for $n = 100$ under four sampling methods (C1-C4).

(a) Simulation plot: $n = 2000$, $p = 0.1$.

(b) Simulation plot: $n = 2000$, $p = 0.5$.

(c) Simulation plot: $n = 2000$, $p = 0.9$.

Figure 3. Histogram and density comparison for $n = 2000$ under four sampling methods (C1-C4).

(a) Simulation plot: $n = 10000$, $p = 0.1$.

(b) Simulation plot: $n = 10000$, $p = 0.5$.

(c) Simulation plot: $n = 10000$, $p = 0.9$.

Figure 4. Histogram and density comparison for $n = 10000$ under four sampling methods (C1-C4).

4. Conclusion

Our study demonstrates the efficacy of inverse-CDF and acceptance-rejection sampling techniques for generating random variates from a complex univariate continuous mixture distribution. Both standalone and hybrid implementations delivered strong performance, particularly at large sample sizes. While minor accuracy degradation occurred in higher-order moment estimation under extreme mixing proportions (e.g., $p = 0.1$ or 0.9) with small samples, this does not diminish the overall utility of these methods.

Both approaches constitute viable strategies for univariate density sampling. When feasible, we recommend inverse-CDF sampling due to its directness and theoretical exactness. However, acceptance-rejection sampling remains indispensable for its broader applicability to distributions lacking closed-form inverse CDFs.

As correctly pointed by a reviewer, robustness and generalizability are desirable and fortunate when they occur. This is a parametric density, and even slight perturbations to the underlying modeling assumptions may lead to substantial changes in inferential results. The simulation design spans a wide range of scenarios and encompasses a broad spectrum of shapes. However, robustness issues present a different challenge. When the density changes, all derivations for the Inverse-CDF method must be revised accordingly, and the choice of the proposal density in the Acceptance-Rejection method may need to be updated. The good news is that both techniques are sufficiently general and flexible to accommodate different density constructions. For example, one could employ alternative versions of the triangular component with varying heights and bases, or different forms of the exponential component, such as truncated or shifted exponentials. The overall conclusions are likely to remain unchanged, provided that derivations and algorithmic steps are carefully adjusted. More specifically, for the Inverse-CDF method, one must ensure that the CDF maps to a valid value in the domain, even when the CDF is flat in certain regions. Similarly, in the Acceptance-Rejection method, the procedure remains valid as long as the proposal density covers all possible values and always dominates a suitably scaled version of the target density.

Author Contribution Statements

All authors prepared simulation design, implementation, compilation of results, paper writing, editing, creating figures, tables etc.

Ethics committee approval

This article does not require ethics committee approval.

Conflict of interest statement

This article has no conflicts of interest with any individual or institution.

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